

The Influence of Motivation, Compensation, and Workcommitment on Work Productivity and Their Impact on the Performance of the Aceh Selatan Environmental Department

Kasputra, A. Sakir*, Teuku Rolillhamsyah Putra

Management Department, UniversitasSyiah Kuala, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: asakirjh1975@unsyiah.ac.id

Abstract: This study aims to examine the motivation, compensation, and work commitment role in work productivity and their impact on the performance of the Environmental Department (DLH)in Aceh Selatan District, Indonesia. The population was all employees of that DLH, totaling 105 people consisting of 35 civil servants and 70 honorary employees. Due to the relatively small population, the sampling method used was the census method. Data was collected by distributing questionnaires to all respondents as measured using a Likert scale. The analytical tool used was PLS. The result proves that all the variables used in this study have not gone well; motivation, compensation, and work commitment affect work productivity; Motivation, compensation, work commitment, and work productivity affect DLH performance; Work productivity partially mediates the motivation and work commitment role in DLH performance; and Work productivity does not mediate the compensation role in DLH performance. These findings explain the DLH performance improvement model in the Aceh Selatan district is a function of increasing worker motivation, compensation, and work productivity.

Keywords:Motivation, Compensation, Work Commitment, Work Productivity, Office Performance

I. Introduction

The Environmental Department (DLH) in Aceh Selatan District, Indonesia, is one of the regional apparatuses formed based on Aceh Selatan District Regulation (Qanun) No 4 of 2020 concerning Amendments to Aceh Selatan District Qanun No 7 of 2016 concerning the Establishment and Composition of Aceh Selatan District Regional Apparatuses. The DLH, which is a government institution that has responsibility for environmental management, is expected to continue to work extra hard and improve performance. This aims not only to maintain the achievements that have been achieved but also to ensure that a green and healthy environment can be realized and maintained.

If we look at all the areas in Aceh Selatan District,it shows its DLH still needs a lot of improvement in managing the environment. Especially in remote areas, plantations, coastal areas, and mining areas where these areas still have the impression that they are not environmentally friendly. Talking about the impact of the environment, the meaning is very broad. An unhealthy environment will have a negative impact on the lives of residents and will even have a huge impact on the economy of the surrounding community.

The Report (LAKIP) of the Aceh Selatan Regency government in 2020 revealed there are still several strategic issues faced by DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency. The issues and problems faced are declining quality of the environment, lack of consistency in law enforcement, not all companies/industries complying with environmental regulations, the potential for pollution increasing, lack of community participation and public awareness in environmental maintenance, lack of processing facilities and infrastructure waste and wastewater, and the lack of area and quality of open space.

Responding to the above phenomena shows that in Aceh Selatan District the DLH still really needs hard work, smart work, and innovation in solving and dealing with these challenges. These challenges and obstacles must immediately receive a response from the leadership of the regional government and the leadership of DLH because if left unchecked they will have an impact on the decline in performance produced by DLH in the future. In addition, the

problem of controlling the quantity and quality of the population's environment and the not-yet optimal participation and role of the community in environmental management that is currently happening shows that the Organizational Performance of the Aceh Selatan Regency Environmental Service as a whole is still low, and urgently needs strategic efforts to improve it.

One of the factors that affect DLH performance is work productivity. Every employee in an organization is required to always have high work productivity so that the targets and goals of an organization can be fully achieved. In public sector organizations, work productivity can be interpreted as the attitude and behavior of employees in the bureaucracy towards the regulations and standards set by the bureaucracy that has been manifested both in the form of behavior and actions (Azharyadi, Musnadi, & Harmen, 2021). In carrying out government affairs, every employee needs to produce high work productivity, especially in providing services to the community.

The work productivity of employees in a public organization in fact cannot be measured materially or financially but can be seen in the completion of the existing volume and workload, and timeliness in addition to the quality of the services they provide. Increasing employee work productivity is inseparable from the level of work discipline established in the organization. Another thing that can increase employee work productivity is the level of knowledge possessed by these employees. Therefore every organization needs to continue to make efforts that can increase employee work productivity such as fostering employee motivation, providing compensation, and increasing work commitment from the employees themselves.

II. Literature

Organizational Performance

An organization is a body established with a specific purpose. A good organization is an organization that can achieve its goals of the organization within a certain period. Government organizations are an extension of the central/regional government in achieving development goals and improving the welfare of society. Every government organization already has goals and performance limits that are regulated based on Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government. The performance of public sector organizations is measured at the end of the fiscal year by comparing target data with realization data. Presidential Regulation No. 29 of 2014 also mentions performance as the output/result of activities that have been or are to be achieved in connection with the use of the budget with measurable quantity and quality. In Minister of State Apparatus Regulation (Permenpan RB) No 53/2014, it is stated that the performance measurement of government agencies is carried out by comparing the achievement of the main performance indicators with work agreements that have been established at the beginning of each fiscal year. Many experts define organizational performance with different meanings, such as (Bari & Alaverdov, 2021) in their book mentions organizational performance as an achievement obtained by an organization by being able to overcome various problems both internal and external, especially during the infodemic period by utilizing and maximizing the role of information technology development.

Work productivity

In every organization, every employee is required to always have high work productivity. High work productivity is possible for every employee to achieve if they know the rhythm of their respective jobs. As reported on the <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/> website page, the purpose of work productivity is to produce/increase products in the form of goods or services as much as possible by utilizing existing resources effectively and efficiently (Thompson, 2019). The high and low productivity of a person's work is inseparable from the knowledge, skills, abilities, attitudes, and behavior possessed by an employee. The State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is the main element of human resources, the state apparatus has a role in determining the success of administering government affairs to achieve government goals in the field of development and the welfare of society. As one of the most important components, the professionalism of government employees is often questioned. The role, function, and position of government officials determine the success or failure of government development programs. Organizational performance can increase if employees in the organization have high work productivity, this can be seen from the indicators of work productivity variables (work attainment, increased work quantity, increased work quality, sufficient working time, accuracy in work, utilization of facilities and company infrastructure, use of time for the benefit of work) is statistically proven to have a contribution in improving organizational performance (Mariska, Musnadi, & Faisal, 2019).

Motivation

Motivation is a person's desire to do something due to encouragement from oneself or from outside the employee. In addition, motivation can also be interpreted as encouraging employees to take action because they want to do it. Theoretically, motivation is inherent in a person. (Robbins & Judge, 2017) states that motivation is a process that explains the intensity, direction, and persistence of an individual to achieve his goals. (Mangkunegara & Octorend,

2015)states: "motivation is formed from the attitude of employees in dealing with work situations in the company. Motivation is a condition or energy that drives employees who are directed or directed to achieve the company's organizational goals. The pro and positive mental attitude of employees toward work situations strengthen their work motivation to achieve maximum performance.Motivation is an important determinant of individual achievement in addition to skills, abilities, and experience(Fachreza, Musnadi, & Shabri, 2018). Every working human being aims to be able to fulfill his life needs, even though the motives for working and the level of needs of each individual are not the same.

Compensation

The main goal of human work is to obtain compensation to meet their needs. Compensation includes direct forms such as base salary, merit, and incentives, and indirect forms such as paid vacations, deferred payments, and health insurance. The ultimate goal of compensation administration is the efficient maintenance of a productive workforce, fair pay, and compliance with federal, state, and local regulations based on what the company is capable of doing.In government organizations, the issue of compensation is regulated in Law No. of 2014 in Article 101 Paragraph (1) "The government is obliged to pay a fair and proper salary to the non-civil servant (PPPK), Paragraph (2) "The salary referred to in Paragraph (1) is given based on expenses work, job responsibilities, and job risks. Paragraph (3) "The salary referred to in Paragraph (1) is charged to the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBN) for PPPK in central agencies and the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD) for PPPK in the regions. Paragraph (4) in addition to the salary referred to in Paragraph (1), PPPK can receive allowances following the provisions of the applicable laws and regulations.According to(Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart, & Wright, 2019)compensation is the total of all gifts given to employees in exchange for their services. The overall interest in providing compensation to attract, retain and motivate employees. Compensation is a segment of human resources administration or administration that focuses on planning, organizing, and controlling the direct and indirect payments that employees receive for the work they do(Kelechi et al., 2016).

Work Commitment

Work commitment is the degree to which an individual is involved in an organization and the strength of his identification with a particular organization which is characterized by three things, namely: belief in the values of an organization, the desire to maintain a relationship with the organization, and a willingness to work for the interests of the organization(Luthans, 2013). (Sopiah & Sangadji, 2018)defines organizational commitment as an important behavioral dimension that can be used to assess an employee's propensity to remain a member of the organization.According to(Noe et al., 2019), Organizational commitment is the degree to which an employee identifies with the organization and is willing to make efforts on its behalf. Employees with high organizational commitment will stretch themselves to help the organization through difficult times. Employees with low organizational commitment tend to leave at the first opportunity for a better job. (Djalil, Indriani, & Muttaqin, 2017)mentions organizational commitment as a combination of emotional ties with the organization which includes moral support and accepting existing values and internal determination to serve the organization.From the several theories that have been described, it can be concluded that organizational commitment is a behavioral dimension that can be used to assess the tendency of employees to stay in an organization during difficult times and do hard work by trying their best to realize the organizational goals.

Framework and Hypothesis

The description of the theory and previous researchdeterminedtheresearch framework that is illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Research Framework

- Ha₁ : Motivation, Compensation, Work Commitment, Work Productivity, and DLH Performance are good.
- Ha₂ : Motivation influences the Work Productivity of DLH.
- Ha₃ : Compensation influences the Work Productivity of DLH.
- Ha₄ : Work Commitment influences the Work Productivity of DLH.
- Ha₅ : Motivation influences DLH performance.
- Ha₆ : Compensation influencesDLH performance.
- Ha₇ : Work Commitment influences DLH performance.
- Ha₈ : Work productivity influencesDLH performance.
- Ha₉ : Motivation influences DLH performance Through Work Productivity
- Ha₁₀ : Compensation influencesDLH performance Through Work Productivity
- Ha₁₁ : Work Commitment influences DLH performance Through Work Productivity

III. Method

This research was conducted at the DLH of Aceh Selatan district, Indonesia. The object was Motivation, compensation, work commitment, work productivity, and Organizational Performance. The population was all employees of the DLH, totaling 105 people (ASN) consisting of 35 civil servants and 70 honorary employees (non-civil servants). The population is presented below.

Table 1. Number of Aceh Selatan DLH Employees

No	Position	civil servant	Honorary / Non-Permanent Employees	Amount
1	Head of Department	1	-	1
2	Secretariat	13	10	23
3	Functional	-	-	-
4	Program field	6	1	7
5	Environmental Management Sector	4	2	6
6	Garbage and Waste Management Sector	4	30	34
7	The sector of Green Open Space Arrangement and Environmental Capacity Building	7	27	34
Amount		35	70	105

Source: Aceh Selatan District DLH (2020)

Due to the relatively small population, the sampling method in this study was the census method. This made it possible to be interviewed through a distributed questionnaire. The census is more accurate because the results can conclude the overall observation results(Sekaran& Bougie, 2016).In this study, primary data collection was carried out using a questionnaire that was distributed directly to all respondents.The answers already exist, all that remains was to choose according to the perception of each respondent.

The questionnaire given to respondents was a questionnaire in electronic form with the help of a Google form. The questionnaire given to the respondents used a closed-question model, thatwas, the questions asked were accompanied by alternative answers beforehand so that respondents could choose one of several alternative answers. Data were measured using a Likert scale. The indicators used in this study are presented below.

Table 2. Indicators

No	Variable	indicator
1	DLH Performance (Z)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Level of community satisfaction 2. Completeness of Facilities and Infrastructure 3. Garbage handled 4. Total maintenance of TPA and IPLT facilities 5. The quality of water quality standards 6. Availability of work information documents 7. Outdoor green open space Permenpan RB NO 53/2014 in the Environmental Service Office of Aceh Selatan
2	Work productivity (Y)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. work achievement, 2. an increase in the quantity of work, 3. work quality improvement, 4. Adequate working time, 5. accuracy in work, 6. utilization of company facilities and infrastructure, and 7. Utilization of time for the benefit of work (Sedarmayanti, 2016)
3	Motivation (X ₁)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The quality of work produced increases. 2. Tasks according to ability, 3. High work initiative, 4. Work relations and 5. Sacrifice (Robbins & Judge, 2014)
4	Compensation (X ₂)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wages/salaries 2. Incentives 3. Allowances 4. Facilitate 5. Housing 6. Cafeteria 7. Sports facilities 8. excursion (Noe et al., 2019)
5	Work Commitment (X ₃)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. work work 2. communication 3. willingness 4. the same value 5. pride 6. inspiration 7. pleasure 8. festivities 9. care (Djalil et al., 2017)

For testing the descriptive hypothesis, this study used SPSS. Direct and indirect hypothesis testing using PLS statistical tools.

IV. Result

Descriptive Test (H1)

The descriptive testing is presented below regarding the one-sample test.

Table 3.H1 Test

Variable	Average	Test Values = 3.41		
		T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
DLH Performance (Z)	3.38	-.387	99	.699
Work productivity (Y)	3.54	1.812	99	.073
Motivation (X1)	3.67	3.102	99	.003
Compensation (X2)	3.32	-1.025	99	.308
Work Commitment (X3)	3.56	1.869	99	.065

Source: Processed Data (2022)

Table 3 above reveals the DLH performance obtains an average 3.38 <3.41 and a sig 0.699>0.05. The work productivity obtains an average 3.54 > 3.41 and a sig 0.073> 0.05. The motivational variable obtains an average 3.67> 3.41 and a sig 0.003 <0.05. The compensation obtains an average 3.32 <3.41 and a sig3.08> 0.05. The work commitment variable obtains an average 3.56> 3.41 and a sig0.065> 0.05. These results indicate that all variables are not good. Thus the testing proves the descriptive hypothesis (H1) is rejected. The results reveal that overall the variables in this study have not fully run well in DLH.

Direct Effect

The test results using the PLS model are shown below:

Figure 2. Analysis of the Research Model

The test results explain the relationship of each variable, namely motivation, compensation, work commitment, work productivity, and performance of DLH. The influence magnitude is presented in Table 4 below

Table 4. Direct Hypothesis Testing

Inter-Variable	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation	t Statistics	P Values
X1_Motivation→Y_Work Productivity	0.448	0.446	0.041	3.176	0.001
X2_Compensation→Y_Work Productivity	0.160	0.176	0.094	3.703	0.045
X3_Work Commitment→Y_Work Productivity	0.318	0.307	0.080	1.970	0.039
X1_Motivation→Z_DLH Performance	0.491	0.492	0.041	3.495	0.000
X2_Compensation→Z_DLH Performance	0.358	0.347	0.040	2.549	0.006
X3_Work Commitment→Z_DLH Performance	0.224	0.222	0.014	2.210	0.000
Y_Work Productivity→Z_DLH Performance	0.228	0.235	0.021	3.229	0.001

Source: Processed data (2021)

Table 4 above shows the direct effect test and the magnitude of the influence in each direct hypothesis test can be seen in the following explanation:

Motivation on Work Productivity of DLHASN (H2)

Testing the motivation role in the work productivity of ASN in DLH provides the t statistics $3.176 > 1.96$ and a $P 0.001 < 0.05$. This proves that hypothesis testing 2 is accepted which means work motivation affects work productivity significantly. This result strengthens the research conducted by (Hertina, Zahirsyah, & Kusramdani, 2021); (Sugiyono & Fakhri, 2021); (Sukriyani, 2021); (Efendi & Yusuf, 2021); (Yudistira, Setyanti, & Sudaryanto, 2018) where it proves that work motivation affects work productivity.

The result also proves the role of work motivation in influencing work productivity is 0.448 or 44.8%, which means that the increasing motivation of ASN will be able to increase the work productivity of DLHASN by 44.8%. These results figure motivation is a very important factor that must always be improved because it can increase productivity. Motivation is an encouragement from within a person to do and complete a job effectively and efficiently and able to produce products in the form of goods/services with high value both in quality and quantity.

Based on the description above and the results of field observations, the leadership in DLH needs to organize a system to increase employee motivation systematically, so that it will be able to increase the work productivity of its employees both in quantity and quality. As for the efforts that must be made by the leadership of DLH to be able to increase the motivation of its ASN work is by continuing to open up space for all ASNs to improvise, and be creative so that these ASNs will have the initiative to be able to continue to improve their performance. Apart from that, the leadership must also reallocate the fields of work for ASNs that are following the areas of ability possessed by these ASNs. This will certainly be able to foster its motivation for ASN which in the end with the suitability of the field of ability with the field of work will also increase the work productivity of the ASN.

Another important thing to do is to provide rewards in the form of providing opportunities for ASN to be able to take part in self-development programs by providing a budget for the program. In addition, the leadership must also foster a sense of togetherness among fellow ASNs within the DLH, as well as provide inspiration, constructive feedback, and information on the latest conditions from the DLH to all of their ASNs. Another step in increasing the motivation of ASN which is very important to be carried out by the leadership of DLH is by being directly involved in providing problem-solving assistance for ASN who are dealing with obstacles and problems so that these obstacles or problems can be resolved immediately.

Compensation on Work Productivity of DLH ASN (H3)

Testing the compensation role in work productivity produces a t-statistic $3.703 > 1.96$ and a $P 0.045 < 0.05$. This indicates compensation affects significantly the work productivity of DLH ASN which means testing hypothesis 3 is accepted. This result strengthens the research by (Hertina et al., 2021); (Sukriyani, 2021); (Efendi & Yusuf, 2021); (Do, 2018); and (Kelechi et al., 2016) where they found that compensation is one factor that has a very important role in increasing the productivity of employees.

The magnitude of compensation's role in affecting the work productivity of ASN in DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency is 0.160 or 16.0%. This value means that if there is an increase in the compensation received by ASN in the DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency, it will be able to increase their work productivity by 16%. Based on the results and the results of field observations, it can be seen that the leadership of the DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency has enormous homework to increase their ASN compensation where the majority of ASNs in the DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency still have a much

lower income than the UMR set by the government. Compensation is one of the variables that have a very large role in increasing ASN work productivity so that in the end it will be able to improve DLH performance as a whole

The measurement of compensation in this study is not only based on the income received but also the facilities received by the ASN at DLH. one of which is sports facilities, where safety is one of the important facilities to be owned by every organization where directly these facilities will be able to provide compensation for the physical and mental health of the ASN. Especially with conditions like today where everyone is required to have good physical health. Physical and mental health can be obtained from exercise. For this reason, it is very important for the leadership, especially in the district Aceh Selatan government to provide good sports facilities that can be utilized by all ASN. Apart from that, maintaining the condition of the sports facilities that are already owned is also very important because with good conditions the sports facilities will be able to be used by all ASN. Especially for DLH, to maintain the physical fitness of their ASN, at least the leadership must provide minimal facilities for a jogging track which all ASN can use to maintain their physical fitness.

Another thing that needs to be done by the leadership of DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency to increase the productivity of their ASN work is to provide rewards in the form of tours/creations. This indicator is rarely applied to all government agencies. However, it might be taken into consideration for the leadership to provide rewards in the form of these activities. Compensation in the form of rewards will automatically be able to become one of the triggers for all civil servants, especially in the DLH to try to be even better in carrying out their duties so that they will be able to significantly increase ASN work productivity and will be able to grow overall organizational performance.

The DLH leaders must re-evaluate the ownership of the official house. Leaders must issue a policy for ASN who already have private facilities in the form of a place to live and also receive official housing facilities but are not used to living alone so that these facilities are returned to the Service so that they can be given to other ASN who do not have their housing facilities or are still renting where they live.

Overall, the leaders need to re-evaluate compensation for ASN, especially ASN with non-civil servant status. Leaders must apply the principle of fairness and equity in providing compensation to all ASNs following the position and efforts of each of these ASNs. Leaders also have to coordinate with the district administration regarding the provision of special wages/salaries for ASN contracts which are still far from sufficient to meet their daily needs where currently the price level of basic goods has started to soar so high that these prices can hardly be afforded. ASN must earn enough to meet the needs of daily life.

Work Commitment on Work Productivity of DLH ASN (H4)

Testing the work commitment role in work productivity ASN in DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency provides the t statistics $1.970 > 1.96$ and a p $0.039 < 0.05$. This result explains work commitment affects significantly ASN work productivity. This also shows hypothesis 4 is accepted. This is supported by (Mariska et al., 2019); (Matahelumual, Adolfina, Raymond, & Kawet, 2019); (Yanti, Musnadi, & Sofyan, 2019); and (Nursanti, 2018) who prove that employee work commitment is one of the factors that influence an increase in productivity.

In this study, the role of work commitment in influencing work productivity was 0.318 or 31.8%, Which means if there is an increase in employee work commitment by 100%, it will be able to increase work productivity by 31.8%. Work commitment can be the basic capital for the organization in achieving its goals. This is because employee work productivity is inseparable from the commitment it has. Based on the results of field observations it can be seen that it is still very important for the leaders in DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency to be able to increase the work commitment of their employees. Work commitment reflects the level of loyalty in working with full dedication to an organization. Work commitment can be interpreted as a situation where an employee side with a particular organization and its goals and desire to maintain membership in the organization. Therefore ASNs who have a high work commitment are urgently needed in organizations where this high commitment will make ASNs dedicate all their time and abilities to achieve the goals of the organization where they take shelter.

It cannot be denied that very few ASNs have a high commitment to their organization. Apart from that, the level of loyalty to the organization, especially the non-civil servant/honorary employee tends to be low. This is known from where if the non-civil servant/honorary employee receives a job offer from another place that promises to provide more benefits in the form of certainty of work position, job title, and even wages, then they will not think twice about staying in the current organization. Things like this are extra work for every leader within the DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency to always try to grow and increase work commitment for their employees.

One of the efforts that must be made by the leaders of DLH to continue to increase their ASN work commitment is to create a harmonious work environment. Where this harmonious work environment will be able to provide a happy attitude at work, and even ASN feel that DLH is a good place to work so they will be very loyal to the organization and will maintain the basic values of the organization and strive to make the organization a much better

organization in the future. Apart from that, the leaders must also be able to inspire all ASN and also be able to be a motivator for all their ASN.

Motivation on the DLHPerformance (H5)

Testing the work motivation role in DLH performance in DLH of Aceh Selatan Regency provides the t statistics $3.495 > 1.96$ and a $p \ 0.000 < 0.05$. This describes hypothesis 5 is accepted which means work motivation affects significantly improving DLH performance in Aceh Selatan District. This is supported by (Sugiyono & Fakhri, 2021); (Sukriyani, 2021); (Itam, Mukhlis, & Musnadi, 2021); (Suwaji, 2019); (Lee & Raschke, 2016) who prove that improving organizational performance is highly dependent on the level of work motivation possessed by employees of the organization.

This study shows that the magnitude of the motivation role in influencing DLH performance is 0.491 or 49.1%. The acquisition of this value shows that every time there is an increase in work motivation from ASN by 100%, it will be able to increase the DLH performance by 49.1%. These results also show that it is very important for the leaders of DLH to be able to continue to work on growing their ASN work motivation. ASN motivation and performance are important tools for the long-term success of DLH. For this reason, DLH needs to take seriously the matter of increasing the work motivation of its ASN.

DLH is a government organization whose performance can directly be felt by the good community such as urban planning, environmental cleanliness, pollution prevention, and environmental maintenance. As previously defined, motivation is an impulse that arises from within a person to achieve a goal that can be caused by both internal and external factors. In this study, it has also been proven that ASN's work motivation has a very large role in improving DLH performance. Therefore it is very important for the leaders of DLH to always try to maintain and foster motivation for their ASN work.

Based on the field observations, the result shows many things still need to be done by the leaders of DLH to increase their ASN work motivation so that it will make a positive contribution to improving overall organizational performance. One of the efforts that must be made is to provide rewards in the form of facilities and funds for each employee who has good performance to be able to take part in self-development programs such as training, workshops, education and training, and certification following their field of work. It is believed that giving rewards in this form will be able to continue to improve the capabilities of ASNs so that the performance produced by ASNs will have even better quality.

Another thing that is important to do is the assignments that are following ASN's field of competence. Nowadays it is very common to find, especially government officials who carry out their duties but are not following their educational background or abilities which in the end makes their motivation decrease and results in poor performance. Therefore it is very important for the leaders of DLH to thoroughly evaluate the burden and function of each ASN and reconstruct the duties and functions of the ASN so that it is following the areas of capability they have.

Maintaining a good working relationship will also be able to motivate ASN so that they will feel comfortable and safe at work which in the end will provide maximum work output or will even able to exceed predetermined targets. Therefore it is important for the leaders to always strive to create a harmonious working relationship within the DLH. This good working relationship can be created by cultivating politeness, a culture of greeting, and a culture of smiles and hospitality. Apart from that, a good working relationship can also be created with activities that are together, such as Gotong Royong (mutual cooperation) and family gatherings.

Compensation on the DLHPerformance (H6)

Testing the compensation role in DLH performance provides the t statistics $2.549 > 1.96$ and a $p \ 0.006 < 0.05$. This shows hypothesis 6 is accepted. These values can also be interpreted that compensation affects significantly DLH performance. This is supported by (Sukriyani, 2021); (Efendi & Yusuf, 2021); (Siwale, Hapompwe, Kukano, & Silavwe, 2020); (Yanti et al., 2019); (Verma, 2018); (Do, 2018) where they also prove that compensation plays a role in efforts to improve organizational performance.

In this study, it can also be seen that the large role of compensation in influencing DLH performance is 0.358 or 35.8%. This value can be interpreted that with increasing work compensation received by ASN, it will be able to increase the performance of DLH by 35.8%. Compensation is a right obtained by someone for services provided to the organization where they work. Compensation is not only in the form of wages but can also be in the form of facilities received. (Do, 2018) stated that it is very important for an organization to always act professionally in providing compensation for the services that have been provided by its employees. The suitability of the compensation received will certainly have a positive effect on the performance they produce so that it will have a good impact on the overall performance of the organization.

Based on the results of field observations, shows that to improve DLH performance through compensation, the DLH leaders need to provide work incentives other than the salary they receive. This incentive will be one of the triggers for ASN work enthusiasm in carrying out their daily duties as community servants at the DLH. apart from that, the leaders must also provide and maintain sports facilities that can be used by all ASNs to exercise so that their physical fitness can be maintained, especially with the current condition which is still colored by the spread of the virus, requiring all ASNs to always have good physical fitness. good. To increase ASN morale, DLH leaders must provide compensation in the form of tourist trips or even umrah for their ASN. This of course will be a huge trigger for ASN to continue to improve their performance so that they will be able to achieve the goals set in an organization. In supporting ASN work operations, DLH must provide official vehicles that can be used by all ASNs in carrying out their duties in the field which so far are known, as official vehicles that can be used by a handful of people with certain positions. Meanwhile, ASNs on duty in the field must use private facilities.

Work Commitment on the DLHPerformance (H7)

Testing the work commitment role in DLH performance in Aceh Selatan District provides the t statistics $2.210 > 1.96$ and a p $0.000 < 0.05$. This figures hypothesis 7 is accepted. The acquisition of this value can also be stated that work commitment affects significantly DLH performance. This is supported by (Mariska et al., 2019); and (Yanti et al., 2019) who also obtained the same results as this study.

The result of this test also provides the amount of work commitment in influencing DLH performance is 0.224 or 22.4%, Which means if there is an increase in ASN work commitment by 100%, it will be able to increase DLH performance by 22.4%. ASNs who have a high commitment to the organization will voluntarily provide maximum effort for the progress of the organization such as trying to achieve organizational goals and maintain organizational values so that it will have an impact on organizational performance. Even with high commitment, it will make ASN willing to sacrifice personal interests including the income earned, or even sacrifice to be willing to leave the organization to achieve the goals of the organization.

Based on the results of field observations, to improve DLH performance through increasing ASN work commitment, the DLH leaders must be able to instill a sense of pride in DLH in all ASN. Leaders must also increase the involvement of ASN in trying to achieve organizational goals so that ASN will increasingly recognize the organization and be bound to its goals. With these efforts, ASN will be able to increase the emotional bond between ASN and DLH which includes moral support and acceptance of existing values, and internal determination to serve their organization.

Work Productivity on the DLHPerformance (H8)

Testing the work productivity role in the DLH performance provides the t statistics $3.229 > 1.96$ and a p $0.001 < 0.05$. The acquisition of these values proves that work productivity affects significantly improving the performance of DLH. these results also prove that hypothesis testing 8 is accepted. This is supported by (Nosike & Okerekeoti, 2022); (Azharyadi et al., 2021); (Kenny S, 2019); (Mariska et al., 2019); (Jyoti & Rani, 2017) where they also yielded the same results as this study.

The test result shows the large role of ASN work productivity in improving DLH performance is 0.228 or 22.8% which means by increasing ASN work productivity it will be able to increase DLH performance by 22.8 %. Productivity is very important for an organization. With high productivity, work will be carried out efficiently and effectively ((Kimsean, 2004) in (Mariska et al., 2019)). Increasing productivity is the dream of every organization to achieve good work results. The low productivity in an organization will have a negative impact on the organization and in the public eye. Productivity relates to human effort or activity to produce goods or services that are useful for meeting the needs of human life and society in general (Ardiansyah, 2018).

Based on the field observations, to improve DLH performance through work productivity, the most important thing to do is to improve the work results of ASN which are accurate and avoid errors. Improving work results can only be done through increasing the capabilities of ASN and supervision carried out by the leaders in each field of their ASN. From the table of respondents' characteristics, it can be seen that 33% of ASNs still have a high school level of education, where the level of education is a reflection of the abilities possessed by their ASNs. One very important effort to be carried out by the leaders of DLH is to provide opportunities for all ASN to be able to take part in formal education programs to a higher level.

The DLH leaders must seek and convey to the leaders of the Aceh Selatan District government and the DPRK regarding the provision of this further study opportunity to issue study permits or study assignments and receive assistance from the local government in financing the burden of this further study as outlined in the Qanun and as well prepare scholarship budgets or educational assistance for all ASNs who wish to attend formal education at a higher level. Apart from that, the leaders of DLH must also allocate a budget for non-formal education programs for all civil

servants within the DLH environment. All ASN in DLH is allowed to be able to take part in self-development programs that are appropriate to their field of work such as training, workshops, training, and certification. With the increased capabilities possessed by these ASNs, they will certainly be able to increase work productivity produced by these ASNs so that organizational goals can be achieved or even exceed predetermined work targets.

Apart from this program, the leaders of DLH must also improve monitoring and evaluation of performance which is carried out periodically for all ASNs, and be directly involved in solving problems or obstacles faced by these ASNs in carrying out their duties, so that work productivity is produced by all ASNs within the DLH can continue to be improved as a whole.

Indirect Effect

Motivation on DLH Performance Through Work Productivity (H9)

Testing the motivation role in DLH performance through work productivity is figured below.

Figure 3. Testing H9

From the results of testing hypothesis 9 using the Sobel calculator as shown in Figure 3 above, the t-statistics is 7,701 > 1,960 and the probability is 0.000 < 0.05. This proves hypothesis 9 is accepted. These values indicate that the work productivity variable mediates the work motivation role in DLH performance. This is in line with (Hadian, 2019); (Suprihatiningrum & Bodroastuti, 2012).

Based on the significance calculation for path C', a mediation chart is figured below.

Figure 4. Mediation Model of H9

Figure 5 above explains path A, namely, work motivation on work productivity, which obtains a coefficient 0.448 and a P 0.001. Path B, namely work productivity on DLH performance, obtains a coefficient 0.228 and a P 0.001. Path C, namely motivation on DLH performance, obtains a coefficient 0.491 and a P 0.000. And Path C', namely the relationship of work motivation and DLH performance through work productivity, obtains a coefficient (0.448 x 0.228 = 0.102) and a p 0.000.

The result in Figure 3 and Figure 4 above reveals productivity partially mediates the motivation role in DLH performance. The magnitude of the productivity in mediating the two variables is equal to 0.102 or 10.2% which means

by increasing employee work productivity will be able to increase work motivation in improving DLH performance by 10.2%.

Work motivation has an important position in achieving organizational goals, this is because the concept of motivation can have a major influence on the progress and movement of an organization in the future. Work productivity can mediate work motivation on organizational performance. This is because employees who have high work motivation will certainly produce high work productivity and in the end have a positive impact on organizational performance.

This result means that improving DLH performance which is influenced by work motivation, can be done by increasing the productivity of their ASN work. Therefore the DLH leaders need to continue to work on increasing their ASN work productivity because, in addition to having a direct impact on improving DLH performance, work productivity is also able to become a bridge to ASN work motivation in improving DLH performance.

Compensation on DLH Performance through Work Productivity (H10)

Testing the compensation role in the DLH performance through work productivity is figured below.

Figure 5. Testing H10

From the test using a calculator as shown in Figure 5 above, it obtained a statistic t score of 1.681 < 1.960 and a p 0.09 > 0.05. The acquisition of this value describes that ASN's work productivity does not mediate the compensation role in DLH Performance in Aceh Selatan District. These results indicate hypothesis 10 is rejected.

Work Commitment on DLH Performance Through Work Productivity (H11)

The result of the hypothesis 11 model test that is the work commitment role in DLH performance through work productivity is figured below.

Figure 6. Testing H11

Testing the work commitment role in DLH performance through work productivity provides the t statistics $3.732 > 1.960$ and a $p\ 0.000 < 0.05$. This reveals that the testing of hypothesis 11 is accepted. These results indicate that work productivity mediates the work commitment role in DLH performance. This is supported by (Mariska et al., 2019); (Wahyudi, 2019).

The significance calculation of C' is presented below.

Figure 7. Mediation Model of H11

Figure 7 above shows path A, namely work commitment to work productivity, provides a coefficient 0.318. Path B, namely the relationship of productivity and DLH performance, obtains a coefficient value of 0.228. Path C, namely the relationship of commitment and DLH performance in Aceh Selatan District, obtained a coefficient value of 0.224. Line C', namely the relationship between work commitment and DLH performance in Aceh Selatan District through work productivity, obtains a coefficient value of $(0.318 \times 0.228 = 0.072$ or 7.2%).

The test results prove that work productivity partially mediates the work commitment role in DLH performance. The magnitude of productivity mediating the two is 7.2%. This explains if there is an increase in the work productivity of ASN in DLH, it will be able to contribute to the effect of work commitment in its role in increasing the performance of DLH by 7.2%. Employee work productivity can be said to be very important for an organization, because whether or not the work productivity of an employee will determine the achievement of the goals (Kimsean, 2004).

Commitment, work productivity, and DLH performance are inseparable. Apart from having a direct role, work productivity is also able to act as a mediator in influencing DLH performance. This has been proven by (Mariska et al., 2019) who in their research proves that besides having a direct effect on organizational performance, work productivity is also able to mediate the organizational commitment effect on organizational performance.

V. Conclusion

The result concludes that the motivation, compensation, work commitment, work productivity, and DLH performance were not good, Motivation influences the Work Productivity of DLH, Compensation influences the Work Productivity of DLH, Work Commitment influences the Work Productivity of DLH, Motivation influences DLH performance, Compensation influences DLH performance, Work Commitment influences DLH performance, Work productivity influences DLH performance, Motivation influences DLH performance Through Work Productivity, Compensation does not DLH performance Through Work Productivity, and Work Commitment influences DLH performance Through Work Productivity. These findings also tell that work productivity partially mediates the motivation and work commitment role in DLH performance, but does not mediate the compensation role in DLH performance. These findings explain the DLH performance improvement model in the Aceh Selatan district is a function of increasing worker motivation, compensation, and work productivity. This finding strengthens the academic model which combines previous models and is tested on a new subject, namely DLH in Aceh Selatan District. Future researchers can further develop the model, strengthen it by adding other variables. This model is also useful for practitioners, especially the research subject, namely DLH Aceh Selatan district in rearranging its performance improvement strategy.

References

- [1.] Ardiansyah, M. (2018). Productivity of the State Civil Apparatus. Retrieved May 5, 2020, from Academia.edu website: https://www.academia.edu/36995379/Produktivitas_Aparatur_Sipil_Negara
- [2.] Azharyadi, Musnadi, S., & Harmen, H. (2021). The Effect Of Leadership Effectiveness And Work Environment On Work Productivity And Its Impact On Performance Of Industry, Trade, Cooperative And Small-Medium

- Enterprises Department Of Pidie Jaya. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 4(4), 257–274. <https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.35409/IJBMER.2021.3296>
- [3.] Bari, M. W., & Alaverdov, E. (2021). *Impact of Infodemic on Organizational Performance*. Pennsylvania, USA: IGI Global Disseminator of Knowledge.
- [4.] Djalil, M. A., Indriani, M., & Muttaqin. (2017). The Influence of Organizational Commitment and Motivation in the Relationship between Budget Participation and Managerial Performance (Empirical Study on Provincial Government Agencies (SKPA) of Aceh Province, Indonesia). *BRAND. Broad Research in Accounting, Negotiation and Distribution*, 8(1), 12–24.
- [5.] Do, T. T. (2018). How spirituality, climate and compensation affect job performance. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 14(2), 396–409. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-05-2016-0086>
- [6.] Efendi, S., & Yusuf, A. (2021). Influence Of Competence, Compensation And Motivation On Employee Performance With Job Satisfaction As Intervening Variable In The Environment Of Indonesian Professional Certification Authority. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 5(3), 1078–1088.
- [7.] Fachreza, Musnadi, S., & Shabri, M. (2018). The Influence of Work Motivation, Work Environment, and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance and Their Impact on the Performance of Bank Aceh Syariah in Banda Aceh City. *Jurnal Magister Manajemen*, 2(1), 115–122.
- [8.] Hadian, D. (2019). Effect Of Job Satisfaction On Work Discipline Mediated By Continuance Commitment. *Jurnal Ekonomi, Bisnis & Entrepreneurship*, 13(1), 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3522777>
- [9.] Hertina, D., Zahirsyah, M. F., & Kusramdani, D. (2021). The Effects of Motivation, Compensation and Communication on Employee Performance Productivity. *Review of International Geographical Education*, 11(3), 1504–1513. <https://doi.org/10.48047/rigeo.11.3.143>
- [10.] Itam, S., Mukhlis, & Musnadi, S. (2021). The Effect Of Motivation And Leadership On Work Performance And Its Impact On Organizational Performance of Environment Department Of Pidie Jaya. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 4(4), 19–34.
- [11.] Junaidi, Musnadi, S., & Majid, M. S. A. (2020). The Effect Of Participative Leadership, Work Discipline, And Training On Employee Performance And Organizational Performance: Study At BKPSDM Pidie Jaya. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 3(1), 17–27. <https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.35409/IJBMER.2020.3135>
- [12.] Jyoti, J., & Rani, A. (2017). High performance work system and organisational performance: role of knowledge management. *Personnel Review*, 46(8), 1770–1795. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-10-2015-0262>
- [13.] Kelechi, N. G., V.O, A., Egwuonwu, Akintaro, Shonubi, & Herbertson. (2016). The Effect of Compensation Administration on Employee Produktivity. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (OMAN Chapter)*, 5(8), 40–47.
- [14.] Kenny S, V. (2019, April). Employee productivity and organizational performance: A theoretical perspective. *Munich Personal RePEc Archive*, 1–10. Retrieved from https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/93294/1/MPRA_paper_93294.pdf
- [15.] Kimsean, Y. (2004). Employee Work Productivity in the Bureaucracy. *Gava Media, Yogyakarta*.
- [16.] Kreitner, R., & Kinicki, A. (2014). *Organizational Behavior Organizational Behavior*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- [17.] Lee, M. T., & Raschke, R. L. (2016). Understanding employee motivation and organizational performance: Arguments for a set-theoretic approach. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 1(3), 162–169. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2016.01.004>
- [18.] Luthans, F. (2013). *Organizational Behavior An Evidence-Based Approach* (8th ed.). New York: Mc Graw Hill.
- [19.] Mangkunegara, A. P., & Octorend, T. R. (2015). Effect of Work Discipline, Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction on Employee Organizational Commitment in the Company (Case Study in PT. Dada Indonesia). *Universal Journal of Management*, 3(8), 318–328. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujm.2015.030803>
- [20.] Mariska, K., Musnadi, S., & Faisal. (2019). Determinant of Organizational Performance with Work Productivity as A Mediation: Case of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) Banda Aceh. *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 2(8), 412–415.
- [21.] Matahelumual, N. P., Adolfina, Raymond, & Kawet. (2019). The Effect of Organizational Culture and Organizational Commitment on Employee Work Productivity at the Regional Secretariat Organizational Bureau of North Sulawesi Province. *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Dan Akuntansi*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.v7i1.22464>
- [22.] Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. H. (2019). *Human Resource Management : Personnel Human Resource Management* (Ed. 15). USA: Harvard Business Review.

- [23.] Noe, R., Hollenbeck, J., Gerhart, B., & Wright, P. (2019). *Fundamentals of Human Resource Management* (8th ed.). United States: McGraw-Hill Education.
- [24.] Nosike, C. J., & Okerekeoti, C. U. (2022). Employee Productivity and Organizational Performance: Evidence from Pharmaceutical Firms in Nigeria of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0). *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 6(4), 108–116.
- [25.] Nursanti, I. (2018). Employee Performance, Organizational Commitment in Employee Work Productivity. *Jurnal Administrasi Pendidikan*, 25(2), 347–361. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.17509/jap.v25i2.15646>
- [26.] Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2014). *Book Organizational Behavior Book 2 (1st Edition; translation D. Angelica, Ed.)*. Salemba Empat.
- [27.] Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2017). *Essential of Organisational Behaviour* (14th ed.). New Jersey: Pearson.
- [28.] Sedarmayanti. (2016). *Human resource management bureaucratic reform and management of civil servants* (5th ed.). Bandung: Repika Aditama.
- [29.] Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Reserach Methods for Bussiness A Skill-Bulding Approach*.
- [30.] Siwale, J., Hapompwe, C., Kukano, C., & Silavwe, D. C. (2020). Impact of Reward System on Organisational Performance: A case study of Brentwood Suppliers Limited in Lusaka, Zambia. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications (IJSRP)*, 10(7), 281–286. <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.10.07.2020.p10335>
- [31.] Sopiah, & Sangadji, E. M. (2018). *Strategic Human Resource Management*. Yogyakarta: Andi Publisher.
- [32.] Sugiyono. (2017). *Business Research Methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- [33.] Sugiyono, E., & Fakhri, F. Y. (2021). The Effect Of Work Motivation, Competency, And Work Culture On Employee Performance And The Impact On Organizational Performance At The Directorate General Of Agricultural Infrastructure And Facilities. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 5(4), 282–294.
- [34.] Sukriyani. (2021). The Effects of Motivation, Compensation, and Work Environment on the Performance of Local Public Officer. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal) : Humanities*, 4(1), 903–917. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.33258/birci.v4i1.1691>
- [35.] Suprihatiningrum, H., & Bodroastuti, T. (2012). Factors Affecting Job Performance (Study on Employees of the Office of the Ministry of Religion of Central Java Province). *Jurnal Kajian Akuntansi Dan Bisnis*, 1(1), 1–23.
- [36.] Suwaji, R. (2019). The Effect of Work Motivation, Leadership and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance Satisfaction and Their Impact on Company Performance. *MAPAN: Jurnal Manajemen Akuntansi Palapa Nusantara*, 4(1), 48–54.
- [37.] Thompson, J. (2019). Factors to Improve Productivity. Retrieved January 26, 2021, from Chron website: <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/factors-improve-productivity-1229.html>
- [38.] Verma, A. (2018). Impact Of Compensation And Reward System On Organization Performance: An Empirical Study. *IJJAR- International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 5(4), 136–140.
- [39.] Wahyudi, I. (2019). *The Influence of Competency and Organizational Climate on Employee Productivity and Its Implications for the Performance of Aceh Regional Secretariat Employees* (Universitas Syiah Kuala). Retrieved from http://103.107.101.35/index.php?p=show_detail&id=56879
- [40.] Yanti, T. D., Musnadi, S., & Sofyan. (2019). Mediating Effects of Knowledge Management, Organizational Commitment, and Compensation on Performance of the District Secretariat of Aceh Jaya, Indonesia. *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 2(6), 270–278. <https://doi.org/10.36349/EASJEBM>
- [41.] Yatipai, T., Montolalu, J., & Kaparang, S. G. (2015). The Effect of Motivation on Work Performance of Study Employees at PT Pos Indonesia Type C Manado. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 3(011), 1–7. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.35797/jab.3.011.2015.8789.%25p>
- [42.] Yudistira, Y., Setyanti, S. W. L. H., & Sudaryanto. (2018). The Influence of Motivation and Training on Work Productivity at Executive Employee PT. Bank Mandiri (Persero) Tbk, Branch of Jember Alun-Alun Through Organizational Commitment. *International Journal of Humanities, Religion and Social Science*, 2(11), 81–91.